

Influence of Teacher Motivation on Students' Academic Performance in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Western Urban District, in Eastern Freetown

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Abstract:- The study was conducted on the Influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance in selected public secondary school. The objectives were; to examine the level of teacher motivation on students' academic performance, assess the impacts of motivation on students' academic performance and identify factors influencing teacher motivation towards effective performance. The study adopted the descriptive research design. The sample size was 50 teachers. Questionnaire was the major instrument used for this study. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages presented in tables) were used to analyze the data. Results revealed that; the earliness or lateness of a teacher in class or school has no influence on the students' performance or does not affect the students' completion of assignments but rather on the content. Interaction of the teacher with the students influences students' academic performance. Reporting time in schools revealed that even though other teacher are late for school students still performed well in continuous assessments and external exams. In-service training influences students' academic performance. Pre-service training is essential to both the teacher and the students. Promotion motivates the teacher. As much as the working conditions of the teacher and teacher remuneration have no direct influence on the students' performance. Based on the results the recommendations were; it is therefore recommended that teachers should be motivated to increase their performance. It is also recommended that the management of public schools put in place measures geared towards enhancing performance of teachers and formulate motivational policies that enhance employee performance. The government can use the study, especially the Teachers Service Commission in acquiring vital information critical for improving terms and working conditions of teachers in order to increase their level of motivation and job performance. The ministry of education can use the findings in understanding extrinsic rewards that lowers teacher's job performance and thus take appropriate strategies and measures so as to improve the efficiency of teachers. The Board of Governors can also provide rewards that give teachers impetus to work harder and facilitate pupils' performance. The government should continue putting more efforts on improving the working conditions by building more

houses with availability of such services as electricity and water for teachers, building laboratories with equipment and improving classrooms conditions and teaching facilities to facilitate easy teaching-learning processes. The Government policies on secondary schools should be well- designed and implemented to meet the demands of teachers and provide them more opportunities for training and development teachers will likely be motivated. The government should make increase on the salaries which reflects the status of teachers and the socio-economic situation prevailing in our societies. The teaching service commission should work towards improving teachers' conditions are made possible. The government authorities through the ministry of finance should provide bikes on loan facilities for male teachers to facilitate there movement to attend school early since they are dominated by male teachers. Increase the number of teachers to reduce the work load of other teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ *Background of the Study*

Education is a universal activity that is part and parcel of human existence. It is by this notion that formal education was set up and it has become a primary and vital process that determines a country's development in terms of technology, economic sector, political sector, and even social sector. Formal education involves many people, i.e. the government, education ministries, society which includes the church, the teachers and the students. According to Richardson (2014), motivation is defined as willingness and desire that makes one be committed to a given activity to achieve specific goals.

Teacher motivation is a desire and willingness to teach using various educative methodology and style when dealing with students (John Marshall Reeve and Yu-Luan Su 2014). In recent years there has been a need to address teacher motivation because of teacher shortages and strikes among teachers. Rebecca Collie, Andrey Martin (2017) in their journal Teaching and Teacher Education found that when a teacher is demotivated, it will have a negative influence on the students since they shall arrive at school late or be absent without any serious reason.

In Kenya, TSC is given the mandate to manage teachers' accordance as stipulated in 2015 Act. Moreover, the TSC are employers of teachers and are in charge of their remuneration and even promotions and impeachment. It is also essential to note the roles of KUPPET to Kenyan teachers. It advocates for sound ethical and professional policies that guarantee job security and fair solution to its members, and its other function is to develop the capacity of members through seminars, symposiums and workshops locally and internationally.

For education to be a success, the teachers and students must have intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Teachers, for instance, are expected to motivate the students in their daily learning interaction for learners to put more effort into their studies hence perform better. Still, teachers cannot successfully do this without motivation, so basically, that is where the teacher motivation title comes in. Teachers being the primary custodians of the knowledge required by the students they must be motivated. It is then essential to find out how their motivation influences the students' academic performance. Elenor Busby (March 2019) the USA in her report recorded that in the helpline for people with a psychological problem it is the teachers who recorded the most calls as compared with people from other professions. The National Education Union also reported that high workloads for teachers jeopardized the mental health of teachers. In Britain Leeds Beckett (2018) in his research on the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance found out that when teachers were poorly motivated, there is a detrimental effect on the performance of the students. The statement, therefore, acts as a driving force of the research to be done in Kenya by looking at three main variables of teacher motivation, i.e. the level of teacher motivation, the impacts of various motivating factors and strategies used by administrators to motivate teachers and how the mentioned variables affect students' performance in academics.

For instance, Conrad Potberg (2015) South Africa; in his research found out that proper and enough educational facilities or infrastructure is one of the things that can motivate or demotivate teachers who in turn share the same effect on their students which affects their academic performance.

In the light of this reality, human capital investment plays significant role in addressing students' performance gaps. Reporting from a study carried out in Singapore on the influence of in-service training on employee performance in state owned organizations, Domack (2012) noted that the most crucial resource for organization is human capital, development through continuous training. It is advised that regular training should be encouraged to renew the employees' vigor in undertaking tasks effectively, as this motivates individual workers to get committed to the ideals of the organization.

From the works of Damian (2012) focusing on factors influencing teachers' work performance in public institutions in the central Sangwang-China, it was observed that teachers

tend to perform well when provided with conducive working environment. She noted that the working environment, not necessarily high pay, if properly improved to satisfaction of a worker, one gets motivated and the output is high.

Studying the influence of extrinsic rewards on teachers' job in public secondary schools in the informal settlements in urban populations in Argentina, Otega (2011), indicated that teachers were hardly motivated and hence it was common to meet learners abandoned in classes, while teachers engaged in informal businesses. The researcher recommended that various incentives ought to be availed to teachers to motivate them so as to dedicate a lot more time with learners.

Observing from the study based on factors influencing students' performance in national examinations in basic educational schools in India, Divili (2008) reported that teacher's performance directly influenced learning outcomes, whose measures are examination results. It is suggested that, working with customers who hardly appreciated the roles teachers play in their life, teachers found themselves in a more challenging working environment, hence needed a lot of motivational rewards to overcome performance bottlenecks.

Zuma (2008), while conducting a comparative survey between teachers' job performance in private learning institutions and those in public institutions in Kwazulu Natal Province in South Africa, established that most teachers in public institutions cited job security as the only advantage enjoyed in public institutions. In stark contrast, most private sector teachers cited improved working conditions and several other fringe benefits on their advantage. Enumerating factors influencing teachers' productivity in public institutions in Nigeria, Emenike (2013) observed that; working conditions, availability of working tools and resources, improved knowledge and skills through regular training, accessibility to information and a sense of recognition, superior remuneration and handsome reward system, are the critical ingredients of worker job performance.

Organizations seeking to remain relevant in their operations within an industry that is characterized by heightened competition must emphasize on investing more in human resource than any other, Ousmane (2013). It was observed in his survey commissioned in Senegal on sustainability of established learning institutions amid rising competition from new arrivals that embracing new technology and new ways of doing things determine institutions ability to renew itself and maintain a competitive edge over rivals. It was also noted that schools that were able to remain relevant in undertaking their key mandates to society focused on the human capital development through superior motivational rewards.

Looking at critical success factors for institutional growth in the public sector in Uganda with particular focus on secondary schools, Tawa (2012) cited training, improved

working environment, handsome salary and wages and motivating rewards as central to teachers' performance. It was suggested that involving the teaching fraternity in making decisions on matters pertinent to the growth of such institutions, creates a sense of ownership hence such teachers will sacrifice for the benefit of the institutions. Polly (2009), like others, in her study on the influence of motivation on workers performance in Rwanda, noted that a feeling of self-worth and recognition by a worker enhance their desires to give much to the organization.

According to Noor (2009), a university student from Dar-es-salaam in Tanzania on a study, focusing on the relationship between job performance and learners' academic performance in national examinations, a pool of factors, working in an interplay, were found to influence academic results. These factors were basically teacher related and bordered on motivational aspect; in service training for gaining more skills and knowledge, better remuneration, material rewards and suitable working conditions.

In Kenya, just like elsewhere, teachers encounter performance challenges, in which irregular work attendance is common, professional documents are rarely prepared, supervision of school activities are ignored, class work are inadequate and generally, learners are literally left on their own, Odul (2012). It was observed that without attempts put in place to motivate teachers, improved students' performance would be difficult to realize. Reporting for a study conducted in Singoiroi Division in the Bomet County on factors influencing teachers' job performance in public primary Schools, Koech (2013) indicated that working environment must be improved to enhance working productivity.

Wanjala (2012), having done a study in Vihiga Sub-County with a focus on the influence of motivation on teachers' work performance, indicated that teaching was a domain that required sacrifices given that most institutions had done very little to motivate them, and this was to blame for perennial poor academic performance.

While giving a report on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in the Sub-County, Rachuonyo South Sub-County Quality Assessment Report (2013) established that there was serious laxity among the teachers in preparing professional and the necessary teaching documents, such as schemes of work, lesson plans of work, supervision of school activities was equally inadequate and learners were insufficiently attended to.

Teresa Kemunto (2013) in her research on the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance found out that training teachers before and during (seminars, conferences, workshops) their teaching profession motivated and in them, updated them and in return had an effect on the academic performance of the students. In Kenya there have been strikes over teachers' pay for instance in 1997, 2003, 2012, 2013 where the strike took twenty-four days, in 2015 the strike took three weeks

and even in 2019 the teachers were about to strike because of how they are motivated by their employers who are the teachers' service commission.

On 13 September 2019, the standard newspaper said that KUPPET were protesting because of a requirement that any teacher who was seeking a principal or deputy principal's post must have a master's degree. The TSC invited online application from teachers who wanted to be promoted, and the master's degree was among the mandatory requirement, the TSC portal automatically blocked teachers without postgraduate qualification. This new policy was to apply even to the current principals, and deputy principals who were to apply again, a situation that would limit most teachers and burr them from promotions and in turn affect them negatively. It is because of these recent happenings that there is need for this research because the administrators need to know how the motivation of the teacher possibly affects students' academic performance.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

The research aims at finding the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance by looking at the four main objectives: Examine the level of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance. The second objective is to assess the impacts of motivation on students' academic performance. The third objective which is to identify factors influencing teachers' motivation towards effective performance. The final objective is recommendations on how teachers should be motivated.

Comparatively, the performance of teachers in public schools and private ones in Sierra Leone, the researcher observed that teachers in private schools tend to perform better than those in public institutions. The performance of learners in internal and external examinations, and that the level of motivation of teachers significantly influenced their general performance.

While giving a report on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in the Western Urban, in Eastern Freetown. School Heads Report (2021) established that there was serious laxity among the teachers in preparing professional and the necessary teaching documents, such as schemes of work, lesson plans and lesson notes. Moreover, it was also observed that more teachers were irregular in their places of work. This study therefore sought to investigate the influence of teacher motivation on student's academic performance in public secondary schools in the Western Urban, in Eastern Freetown.

Oguta (2012), observed that performance of an individual teacher directly corresponds to the performance of learners in internal examinations, and that the level of motivation of teachers significantly influenced their general performance. He concluded that learners' performance was substandard because teachers did not display commitment to duty.

➤ *Aim of the Study*

The purpose of this study is to investigate and find out the influence of teacher motivation or impact on students' academic performance in selected public secondary schools in the Western Urban District, in Eastern Freetown.

➤ *Objectives of the Research*

In precise the research was to:

- Examine the level of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance.
- Assess the impacts of motivation on students' academic performance.
- Identify factors influencing teachers' motivation towards effective performance
- Recommendations on how teachers should be motivated

➤ *Research Questions*

The research was guided by the following questions:

- How does the level of teacher motivation affect students' academic performance?
- How does the impact of motivation on teachers affect students' academic performance?
- Which factors influencing teachers motivate can be used to ensure effective performance?
- What strategies can be used by authorities to motivate teachers?

➤ *Significance of the Study*

The study hopes to act as a foundation to teacher motivation researches in Western Urban District. It was hoped that this research study would be significant to teachers in Public Secondary Schools in Eastern Freetown, for they would gain information on how to improve their performance in various engagements.

The study hopes to provide findings that will be used by administrators to ensure teachers are motivated since they shall know how much their teaching staffs are motivated hence the students' academic performance could be improved.

The study hopes to advocate to academic stakeholders motivating factors that affect teachers in the process affecting students' academic performance.

Besides, teachers at different levels of education, basic, tertiary, as well as higher education would equally benefit significantly from the study results by obtaining best human capital management practices to enhance job performance, for the benefit of both individual worker and the organization.

Moreover, the study would also be significant to the management of public schools to gain insights into measures geared towards enhancing performance of teachers and formulate motivational policies that enhance employee performance.

The government also stands to benefit from the study, especially the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) in acquiring vital information critical for improving terms and working conditions of teachers in order to increase their level of job performance.

The findings also may help the Board of Management (BOMS) in providing rewards that give teachers impetus to work harder and facilitate students' performance.

➤ *Scope and Delimitations of the Study*

The research study focused on the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Western Urban District, in Eastern Freetown. Of particular interest in the study were teachers on TSC Payroll who are deployed to teach in public secondary schools in Eastern Freetown. These schools were geographically spread in the entire three wards, reflecting deferent characteristics on Mixed Day schools. The final study findings would be generalized on the target population from where the sample was drawn.

➤ *Limitations of the Study*

This study was on exploring the influence/impact of the teacher motivation on students' academic performance in public schools. The study was limited by a number of factors, such as financial constraints and time. The time and funds allocated for the study were not enough to reach all public schools and so only few were selected to be researched as it was done in Eastern, Freetown with its geographical vastness. The study was also be limited by insufficient resources for developing the research instruments and spending on other research related activities, Non- availability of data and relevant documents was another limitation. Moreover, the study was also be constrained by unwillingness of some respondents in giving information as a consequence of unexplained suspicions. Despite the limitations, the researcher was able to gather enough data as per research objectives and questions. However, these limitations were overcome by employing strategies such as visiting respondents on motorbikes, operating within the budget and also informing the respondents of the significance of the study as well as disclosing statement of confidentiality between the researcher and the respondents, that any information obtained would strictly be used for academic purposes only and never divulged to any other person, whatsoever.

➤ *Definition of Key Terms*

- **Motivation:** Those external and internal factors that stimulate desire and energy in a teacher to be continually interested in and committed to his or her teaching job, and to exert persistent effort in ensuring students perform well in exams.
- **Performance:** For the purposes of this study, performance will refer to the student's average outcome in exams.

- **Public Secondary school:** A learning institution in the 6-3-3-4 system joined after class six. Public school also refers to a school developed and maintained by public fund from the government, parents and community.
- **Teacher:** A person appointed by the T.S.C. to teach children in a secondary school.
- **Influence:** Factors that contribute to a result or outcome.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Introduction*

This chapter is made up of various reviews done in the past that are related to this research topic and its main objectives. It also involves the theoretical framework which provides information on various motivation theories that will be used in the research.

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

The Study Majored on Three Theories of Motivation. They Include:

- Victor Vrooms Expectancy Theory;
- Theory is the Maslow’s Theory of Motivation
- Hertzberg’s Theory of Motivation

Firstly, Victor Vrooms Expectancy Theory suggests that motivation is a cognitive process where one believes that the more they put effort into particular works, the more the performance and the more the reward. It is from this theory that the level of teacher motivation will be approached from since the attitude, attendance of a teacher and the relationship they have with their students determine the kind of effort they are putting which will, in turn, affect students’ performance which in this case is the reward. According to this theory, the teacher will be and is expected to put more effort into teaching so as the performance of students can be greater. This also applies to the administration that has to keep the teachers motivated to facilitate good performance from students.

Secondly, according to Maslow’s Theory of Motivation, there is a hierarchy of needs in human beings that determine human motivation. These needs are to be met in their order, i.e., psychological, security, belonging, self-esteem and then the prestige needs. In this study, the psychological condition is part of the intrinsic motivation. This is mostly achieved during the pre-service motivation, security which is achieved through the salary of the teacher, belonging that involves the relationship of the teacher and student (interaction), self-esteem that is achieved through in-service training, and the prestige needs that are achieved in the working conditions and also promotion. When these needs are met, there is positive feedback from the result of the students, and when not met, the adverse effects are achieved. It is for these reasons that a teacher is ranked according to students’ performance.

Finally, Hertzberg’s Theory of Motivation is concerned with the extrinsic motivators which are controlled by the administration, leader, or manager. According to

Hertzberg, recognition, advancements, achievement, responsibility, and characteristics of work itself are the intrinsic motivators that promote job satisfaction and salary, rules and regulations, working conditions, and technical supervision are the extrinsic motivators that determine dissatisfaction or fulfillment of an individual in the job.

It is, therefore, essential that the employers of teachers (TSC) and the ministry of education control these extrinsic motivators to motivate teachers and hence promote students’ academic performance.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

This study has two main variables, the dependent variable, which is Students’ academic performance and the independent variable, which is influence of teacher motivation. The independent variable is further divided into other variables according to the three objectives of the research as illustrated below in a table. The table illustrates the relationship between the independent variables which is derived from influence of teacher motivation and the dependent variable which is students’ academic performance.

In precise the relationship between the two variables is what the study’s main concern is.

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework
Source: Copied from Author 2020

➤ *Concept of Employee Motivation:*

According to Behnaz (2013), motivation can be defined as a psychological process that can drive and stimulate an individual which can be either to attain the top list in the sales target or else to be a goof team player. Motivation can also be the strength of an individual’s behaviour to drive him/her to attain their targets and thereby improving their productivity (U.S, 2013). When an employee’s needs and requirements are met by the organization/management, it creates an enthusiasm and interest among the employees to work for the collective goals and objectives of the organization either at group or individual level (Haque et al, 2014).

Henceforth, there is a lack of consensus in regards to what actually necessitate employee motivation? Whether it is psychological process, behavioural trait or mere personal achievement, and if so, how important is motivation in an organization? As per the founder of Virgin Atlantic, financial and non-financial motivating factors play a major role in participating employees in the succession of any multinational corporation (Dudovsky, 2012).

As per Sir Richard Branson (Virgin.com) 'If it weren't for a bunch of well trained, motivated and, above all, happy people doing their bit, we'd have never launched a record label, never mind a fleet of 747s'. In 2014, Google was selected as the "Best Company" and they well accepted for their outstanding activities in motivating their employee. And this recognition was given to Google on fifth year running by the Great Place to Work Institute and Fortune Magazine (Martin, 2014). As per the Vice President of People Development at Google (Fast Company, 2013) 'It's less about the aspiration to be No. 1 in the world, and more that we want our employees and future employees to love it here, because that's what's going to make us successful.'

➤ *Level of Teacher Motivation*

According to Javaid (2009) the level of teacher motivation and morale of teachers is determined by their conditions of living, conditions of working which then affects their performance in classroom. This implies that the level of teacher motivation is affected by various factors and it in turn affects their performance, attendance and even relation with students.

● *Class Attendance*

In Kenya, secondary school lessons are allocated forty minutes and teachers are supposed to deliver exhaustively on a topic. Therefore, teachers have to be in class on time to ensure that the teaching time is maximally used.

For effective learning, a teacher is supposed to employ various teaching methods, strategies and style. Therefore, teachers have to prepare adequately for the lessons. At the end of the day the teachers shall have played various roles in class i.e. as a planner, motivator, decision-maker and also a craftsman. As Richardson (2014) states, motivation is the interaction of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to perform certain work to achieve goals just like the conscious and unconscious factors work hand in hand. This statement, therefore, implies that the level of teacher motivation will work hand in hand with how they appear in class, teaching method and interaction with students.

Atkinson (2000) found out that demotivated teachers lacked enthusiasm in both teaching and in students work while motivated teachers had the enthusiasm and even looked forward to attend lessons and to meet their students. For instance, marking the students' work and giving extra tutorials and extra work is only possible when the teacher is well motivated.

Orji (2014) further adds that how well a teacher performs is reflected by the students' performance. Motivated teachers always teach their students well delivering all their expertise to the students but then when they lack intrinsic motivators like loving their work and extrinsic motivators like salary then their morale reduces and this can lead to reduced focus on teaching which is reflected by how late they attend lesson, how they deliver and also how early they leave the classes.

A research carried out by International institute for educational planning found out that absenteeism can be as high as 25% in other countries and this always has a negative impact on the students who are not taught and at the end of the day do not achieve the objectives of the syllabus.

● *Interaction with Students*

In every learning institution there are always teachers, students, learners and support staffs, but for syllabus and education objectives to be fulfilled, it is teachers and students who must work hand in hand. Therefore, there must be positive teacher-student interaction for effective learning. In dealing with interaction of teachers with students, we looked at the how a teacher appreciated the students' attempts, to what extent a teacher went to improve the students' performance and how the teacher motivated her learners.

According to Ken Ayo Azubuike and Orji Friday Oko (2016), in their research on impacts of teachers' motivation on the academic performance of students: implication for school administration notes that the behavior of a child is always influenced by how the response and reaction of the teacher is on his or her behavior and actions. According to Boss and Vaughn (2002) it is important for teachers to recognize positive and desirable actions of students and let know they have to observe such at all times rather than only pointing their weaknesses and be verbal on them a situation that is usually there with the teachers. It should always occur to teachers that students are different and they are differently motivated, therefore, they should use different methods but then this kind of knowledge requires a teacher to be well-motivated so as to exercise patience with slow learners or geniuses in class without demotivating or insulting them. It is important for students to know teachers have high expectation for them, hence they cannot allow them to quit (Carter, 2000). Lavoie (2007) reiterates that without motivation there is no learning.

Reinforcement always strengthens the behavior to which they are directed (Ayo and Oji, 2016). When a negative reinforcement is given to a student who gives an attempt in class then there is a high chance that the student will not try again in future. It is with this reason that teachers' emotions should be intact with no anger, despise or negative attitude towards a student. Birch and Ladd (1997) positive teacher-student relationship had an essential role of developing competence in a school, solved problems, and boosted the self-esteem and attention of students, which makes students perform better, and the result motivates

teachers.

Davis and Ashley (2003) study preferred that teachers should put more effort in developing a good relationship with the student, which will make teachers creative in their delivery and, in turn, make the students feel safe and motivated to take intellectual risks. Successful teacher relationship makes students feel capable, and only this can be achieved when teachers are motivated since “no blind man can lead another blind man.”

- *Reporting Time in School*

In Kenya, all teachers are expected to be in school from eight in the morning to five except during Fridays and Mondays when they have to be present for parade meetings with the students. Reporting time of teachers is one of the factors that will help determine the level of teacher motivation since lateness without reasonable excuse is, of course, a sign that a teacher is not motivated and of the cause, as Leeds Beckett (2018) puts it, low motivation of teachers will have a detrimental effect on the performance of the students.

- *Impact of Motivation*

Factors that motivate and keep the motivation of teachers intact are many, but this study was to focus on:

- *In-service Motivating Factors (seminars, conferences, and workshops)*

By 1981 in-service training was already an active process for all teachers. Uche (1981) and Cross River State Government Reports (1979) confirmed that teachers who went for in-service training performed better than those who did not go for in-service training. De Jesus and Lens (2005) found out that in-service motivation played a big role in motivating teachers which in turn influence the academic performance of the students.

Adeyemo Adeyinka and Omisore Adedotun (2013) suggested that conferences, workshops and seminars boost the growth and morale of teachers to teach students. In Greece, other than inductive training, the in-service training is optional and its aim is to support the implementation of innovative subject for high schools and it is provided by The National Organization for Teachers Training from June 2011.

In Kenya, in-service training is referred to as Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and is done to strengthen teachers professional understanding, role, context, self and sharing knowledge and activities across schools. (Githara, P.M. 2010).

Ministry of Education is the body that provides CPD courses to secondary schools in Kenya through the Kenya Education Sector Programme (KESPP). These programs are offered mostly during the April, August, and December holidays. In-service trainings are important because they foster continuous professional growth by keeping the teachers abreast of new development in their area of

specialization and promote competence. Eduwen Osamwonyi (2016) states that in-service training is necessary because it enhances work performance and motivates the teacher in the field of education. It's therefore a necessity and a factor that motivates the teacher other than just keeping the teachers updated with the current innovations. When teachers attend the conferences, seminars, and workshop, they acquire knowledge which boosts their confidence and develop their intrinsic motivation. When they are back from the training, they employ the new skills that automatically reflect on students' academic performance.

- *Pre-Service Training*

Pre-service training is a long process. For instance, in Kenya, secondary school teachers have to undergo pre-service training of three years for those who are graduating with a diploma and four years for those graduating with a degree. These teachers have a term or a year of teaching practice and as from 17 October 2019, the TSC decided and even announced internship vacancies for ten thousand teachers before they are fully employed. Other than just trying to accommodate the high demand of teachers due to 100% transition, it is a way of motivating these trainee teachers who could be jobless for a long time and feel frustrated with education. Moses Ochanji, Nicholas Twoli, Bwire and John Maundu (2015) in their study on Mentoring in Pre- service Teacher Education: The Case of a Developing Country, Kenya suggest that pre-service training mentors and also promotes development by equipping teachers with skills that give them confidence in their work.

- *Factors Influencing Teachers Motivation*

Organizational strategies used to motivate teachers are also part of the motivating factors for the teachers. The study looked at other motivating factors controlled by the administration that motivate teachers' morale and also affect students' academic performance. The study was interested in working conditions, teacher remuneration, and promotion of teachers.

- *Working Conditions*

Enoch Rabotapi (2016) suggested that teachers should be motivated in particular, new teachers are supposed to be taken through an induction to ease their transition into the work environment. This is probably because adapting to a new environment is not easy, and it can affect their interaction with the students hence affect students' performance.

Chrispen Chiome (2016) advocates that teachers should be motivated by administrators by ensuring teachers are well informed and equipped to work in the 21st century. They need to be up to date with technology. This will also help the teacher give advanced examples in class and in turn improve students' performance.

According to Anjali Sharma (2016) the working conditions of teachers have a positive correlation with the motivation of the teacher. Every administration should, therefore ensure there are necessary facilities that motivate

teachers and keep them on toes. For instance, lack of facilities like printers or fullscaps, charts, chalks, staffroom equipped with chairs can demotivate teachers and also limit the way they teach, i.e., teaching method and morale of the students hence poor performance can be noted.

According to Clement Croome (2000), environment affects job performance and job satisfaction Dilani adds that there is a link between the health of an individual and the work environment by considering the sanitation, lighting, and air freshness in the rooms. Teachers' wellbeing must be prioritized by ensuring this and their morale to be boosted by keeping their environment and the classes favorable.

Diana Wanja Gitonga (2012), in her research on the influence of teacher motivation on students' performance in KCSE, suggests that the working condition of a teacher involves classroom conditions, workload, distance from home to work, means of communication in school, and available facilities in the school. All these have to be favourable for a teacher to be motivated enough to do his/her work.

Conrad Potberg (2015), in his research, found out that proper and enough educational resources and facilities /infrastructure is one of the demotivating factors that affect students' academic performance.

- *Promotion*

According to TSC act section 35, it is the TSC that is in charge of promoting teachers in Kenya every year. Asiago Lenah, Dr Walter Okibo, Dr. Andrew Nyangau, and Cleophas Ondima (2015), in their research on the effects of non-financial incentives on job satisfaction of teachers in public secondary schools, found out that most teachers were demotivated by the fact that promotions from the TSC took long yet promotions was one of the main factors which boosted their morale and gave them more reasons to stay on their jobs longer that is until retirement.

- *Remuneration*

It is monetary benefits that teachers get, for example, salary, allowances, pensions, medical cover. It is what attracts and keeps one in a particular job or career because their economic and basic needs are taken care of by the money. Archingbong (2013) for education to be a success, there must be a continuous effort from stakeholders to provide the right working conditions, incentives, and remuneration. These are what make the teacher go to school, prepare for lessons, arrive early, and motivate learners.

Prem Gaire (2015) states that when administrators provide timely pay and increase their income yearly, then teachers would be motivated to improve their performance. In Kenya, there have been several teachers' strikes based on the low salary in Kenya, and during the strikes, the students are not usually taught.

- *How to Motivation Teachers*

According to Okumbe (1998) motivation is defined as a physiological or psychological deficiency or need that activates behaviour or a drive that is arrived at a goal or incentive. According to Balunywa (2003), motivation is the inducement of a desired behavior with in subordinates. It is the inducement of a desired behaviour within subordinates. Hornby (2000) on the other hand defines motivation as an incentive to act or move. Webster's dictionary (2002) defines the concept motivation as the act or process of moving or drive, or an incentive. In this study, the variable motivation involved both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators.

- *Extrinsic Motivation*

According to Sansone & Harackiewicz (2000), extrinsic motivation results from the attainment of externally administered rewards, including pay, material possessions, prestige, and positive evaluations from others. In this study, extrinsic motivation of teachers included externally administered rewards like salary, free accommodation, free meals, weekly duty and extra teaching allowances, advance payments in case of financial problems, leave of absence and free medical care among others.

- *Intrinsic motivation*

Intrinsic motivation is an inducement derived from within the person or from the activity itself and, positively affects behavior, performance, and well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2000). In contrast to extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation is said to exist when behavior is performed for its own sake rather than to obtain material or social reinforcers. In this study, intrinsic motivation of teachers included job satisfaction of derived from teaching, enjoyment of teaching, the challenging and competitive nature of teaching, recognition, career development, control over others and, teaching as one's goal in life.

- *Summary of Literature Review and Uniqueness of the Study*

This chapter reviewed the literature related to the "influence on teacher motivation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools and factors affecting the teachers" motivation. It shows the definitions of the key words, which are motivation and academic performance. The chapter also discussed the motivation theories whereas, "Motivation- Hygiene Theory, Maslow Theory and Expectancy Theory are selected to guide the study. From the foregoing literature however, it has been clear that no study had been conducted to assess the "influence on teacher motivation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools teachers in Portee Community, in Eastern Freetown.

Therefore, a research gap was evident in investigating whether motivation of teachers increased their morale to perform as well as the effect on the performance of students. This study investigated and provided information to close the above mentioned research gaps. It is clear that positive reinforcement results in improved performance and hence there is need for a review on the current ways of motivating teachers.

The reviewed of empirical, help a researcher to identify the research gap that will help to fill the present study. The Uniqueness of the research is the rationale behind the choice of Portee Community in Eastern Freetown is the fact that, there are very few, if any, researches done on the related topic in the area. The next chapter focus on the methodological procedures employed to realize the study objectives.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ Introduction

This chapter reviews the research design that was used, the study area, the target population, the sampling technique that was used, the sample size, measurement of variables, research instruments that were used, validity and reliability of the research, the data collection technique, data analysis, and finally logistical and ethical considerations.

➤ Research Design

Kothari (2004) defines research design as the arrangement of the conditions for the collections and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was used to investigate a population by first determining samples to be used to determine occurrences. This design was used because it gave the researcher the time and room

to research on motivating factors broadly, strategies used by the administration to encourage teachers and also the level of teacher motivation and finally find out the relationship between the above and students’ academic performance. The descriptive survey was considered the most appropriate one, as Orji (2011) points out that it is best if the researcher intends to get information and responses from a large population.

➤ Study Area

The research was carried in the Portee Community in Western Urban District in Eastern Freetown. There have been many kinds of research on the influence of teacher motivation on student academic performance. Still, there is no documented research on the Influence of Teacher Motivation on students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Portee Community in Eastern Freetown. It is for this reason that the researcher was interested in this specific area.

➤ Population of the study

The study was carried out among teachers in two public secondary schools in Eastern Freetown. The teachers that were considered are graduates, holders of diplomas and certificates in education since these are considered to be qualified teachers. The research population was of one hundred teachers from the public secondary schools in Portee Community, in Eastern Freetown.

Table 1 Population of the Two Secondary Schools

Teachers in school type	Total Population	Sample Size	Sample Percentage
Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School	50	25	50
Umar Bin Al-Khattab Islamic Secondary School	50	25	50
Total	100	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

The table above indicates that there are 50 teachers in Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School and 50 teachers in Umar Bin Al-Khattab Islamic Secondary School sum up total 100 teachers. This constitutes the population of the study.

➤ Sample and Sampling Procedure

Table 2 Summary of Sample Selection Procedure for the Two Schools

Schools	Umar Bin Al-Khattab Islamic Secondary School	Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School	Total
Respondent s	25	25	50

Source: Field Data 2021

The table shows that 50% of the teachers/respondents of these schools were selected for this research. Twenty five (25) respondents were selected from Umar Bin Al-Khattab Islamic Secondary School and twenty five (25) respondents were selected from Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School. Therefore, the sample size constitute of 50 teachers.

• Sample Size of the Study

A sample is a small proportion selected for observation and analysis (Omar, 2011). By observing the characteristics of the sample, a researcher can make certain inferences about the characteristics of the population from which it is carefully drawn. Contrary to some popular opinion, samples are not selected haphazardly or carelessly. They are chosen in a systematic or random way so that chance errors are

minimized and probabilistic reasoning involved in generalizations can be utilized. For this study, simple random sampling technique was used in selecting public secondary schools.

According to Sutton and David (2004), state that a sample size should not be less than 30% of the study population which is beyond basic description, it would be difficult for the researcher to get accurate information.

Overall, 100 teachers were the targeted participants in the study (50) teachers as primary respondents; are selected for the study.

The sample for the study comprised of 50 teachers and 25 teacher from each compass making a total of 50 teachers and which was 50% of the population which was 100 in total. This was backed up by Kothari (2003) that sample sizes greater than 30 tends to reflect a normal distribution trend which has validity for generalization. However, the study employed two sampling procedures that was; purposive sampling, to select schools and simple random sampling to get respondents.

- *Sampling Procedure*

In this study, the respondents were secondary school teachers teaching in schools within Eastern Freetown. Portee Community has three wards.

Based on this, the sample of this study was selected using three techniques, namely stratified random, simple random and purposive sampling techniques. These techniques were used to select those elements judged to be typical or representative of the population, which ensured that a certain segment of the population was represented in the sample, and ensured equal chances of being selected (Kothari, 2004; Manion & Morrison, 2006; Omari, 2011).

Purposeful sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources (Patton 2002). This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups of individuals that are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Cresswell and Plano Clark 2011). In addition to knowledge and experience, Bernard (2002) and Spradley (1979) note the importance of availability and willingness to participate, and the ability to communicate experiences and opinions in an articulate, expressive, and reflective manner. In contrast, probabilistic or random sampling is used to ensure the generalizability of findings by minimizing the potential for bias in selection and to control for the potential influence of known and unknown confounders. Purposively teachers were selected as respondents in this study.

- *Instruments for Data Collection*

The research employed the use of questionnaire and focus group discussion guide. Questionnaire was used because teachers can read and write and because it collect more information over a short period. (Orodho, 2012). Since the research aimed to keep the compiled data anonymous, questionnaire proved to be the best instrument for the study. The study was broad with limited time, making questionnaire the best data collection tool. The researcher designed questionnaires which focused on teachers' profile as well as motivation from intrinsic and extrinsic perspectives. The aim of using this method is to get a broad - based view of the respondents.

The first section of teachers' questionnaire contained teachers' personal factors such as level of education, number of years in teaching, qualification and marital status. Teaching and learning related materials and the environmental factors such as perceived quality of facility

and equipment, administration support, amount of teaching time, class duration and class size were also collected in the first part of the questionnaire. The second section covered teachers' motivation level and factors affecting teacher's motivation in public secondary schools and the last covered impact/influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance.

The questionnaires included two types of questions. These are close-ended and a few open ended questions. In closed ended questions respondents were restricted to a series of pre-determined answers. In case of open ended questions the respondents were encouraged to express themselves more freely.

Focus group discussion (FGD) is conducted through discussions in more than one person at a time (Leedy and Omrod, 2001). The discussion provided an opportunity for the researcher to discuss in depth issues with a relative large group of people in relative short time. Secondly, throughout the discussion, participants heard each other's experiences and made additional comments beyond their own original comments. FGDs were used with the teachers to get their views on influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance. The discussion took place after normal class hours so as to avoid disrupting normal teaching. One group constituting a total of eight teachers in each public secondary school was involved in FGD. The researcher led the discussion. Denscombe (1998) maintains that a sample of 6-12 is big enough to generate sufficient information and data from focused group discussion.

- *Validation*

The quality of research depends on the design of research instruments as well as application of these instruments in data collection in the field. There are several criteria or tests for judging the quality of any empirical research. These include validity and reliability (Easwaran and Singh 2010) and how each was achieved is discussed.

- *Validity of Instrument*

Validity is the extent to which the instruments used during the study measure the issues they are intended to measure. To ensure validity of instruments, the instruments were developed under close guidance of the supervisor. After the questions are designed, they were pre-tested to a tenth of the teachers in the sample. The questionnaire contained questions generated from the research objectives and conceptual framework. This helped to identify ambiguous questions in the instruments and be able to realign them to the objectives. The items were checked before being administered to ensure they were relevant and understandable.

- *Reliability of instrument*

Reliability is the extent to which the measuring instruments will produce consistent scores when the same groups of individuals are repeatedly measured under the same conditions. The study employed the test-retest method to ensure the reliability of the information collected, which confirmed the correlation co-efficiency provided a

measure of stability. In this research, reliability was achieved by first pre-testing structured questionnaires and semi structured interview protocol with five respondents from the target population and experts in the field to obtain consistency and accuracy. Their comments and corrections were incorporated in data collection instruments and re-tested prior the use in the field. The study administered one type of questionnaire to teachers and using reliability test, were attained implying that the tool was suitable for assessing the influence of teacher motivation on student academic performance in public secondary schools in Western Urban District, in eastern Freetown.

➤ *Sources of Data*

The study used both sources of data, primary source and secondary source, mainly based on qualitative data and quantitative data. Basically qualitative data focused on respondents' perceptions towards the respective study's objective, which was exploring the influence of teacher motivation on student academic performance in public secondary schools in Eastern Freetown. On the other hand, quantitative data focused on frequencies and percentages with regards to the relevant data that was collected from the respective respondents.

Primary data are those data collected afresh and for the first time and mostly are original in character. In this study, one research instruments was used to collect primary data which include self-administered questionnaires. The primary data were based on the research questions of the study.

Secondary data are the data that is already exists in published reports, books and internet. Accordingly, secondary data consists of readily available compendia and already compiled statistical annual reports that data may be used by researchers for their studies. In this research, the secondary data was collected from reviewing existing research works of other researchers that are related to the study.

➤ *Method of data collection*

The researcher was personally distributing a total of 50 questionnaires to teachers (the respondents) in the study area and collected later at a time agreed with the respondents. According to Bell 1993, Touliatos and Campton 1988 the use of questionnaires is the only way to achieve collecting data that has the respondents' views, attitudes, feelings, and opinions. Hence, it's the most effective instrument for this research. Teachers were gathered in the staffroom to avoid inconveniences. Thereafter, questionnaires were distributed to each teacher and the researcher directed them on how to fill in the questionnaires. Teachers were given enough time to fill them. In administering questionnaires, there were requests from the researcher to teachers to answer honestly in order to ensure that genuine information from respondents was obtained. Subsequently, all questionnaires were collected from all respondents and on average it took 45 minutes to complete filling each questionnaire.

➤ *Method of Data Analyses*

Data analysis is the separation of data and the examination of the data to determine its parts about the real data collected. The research used descriptive analysis. This study used quantitative and qualitative techniques to analyze the collected data from questionnaires. The results were summarized in terms of the study's objectives and presented in tables and explanations.

● *Quantitative Data Analyses*

In this technique, descriptive statistics of frequency tables were used to analyze and present the data from questionnaires. In particular, frequency, percentages are presented in tables and as a means of presenting data. Data was analyzed and interpreted as per research objectives.

● *Qualitative Data Analyses*

Qualitative data from Interview scripts, notes and statements were systematically coded, and classified into broad descriptive categories - exploring themes, meanings and/or issues that emerged from the information gained from interviewing. These data were further linked to the research objectives/questions to generate meaning of the study topic.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

In terms of ethical considerations, the researcher acquired an introduction letter from Njala University and a self-written letter to ask for permission to carry out the research. Then the researcher sought appointments with the schools involved in the study through the school principals. The researcher then administered questionnaires personally. The researcher also ensured that the research did not interfere with the school programs by administering questionnaires during lunch time.

The respondents were made aware of the purpose of the research before taking part in the study and to ensure privacy and anonymity. The respondents did not write their names or names of the schools in which they teach. After the analysis of the data, the answered questionnaires were destroyed.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Introduction*

This chapter focuses on an in-depth data analysis, presentation, interpretation, and discussion. Also, this chapter represents the data collected by the questionnaires that were returned by the respondents and analyzed. The study was aimed at finding out the influence of teacher motivation on student's academic performance in selected public secondary schools in Western Urban District, at the Portee Community in Eastern Freetown. Data analysis was done against the backdrop of the key study variables. The findings of the data are described systematically, as illustrated in the conceptual framework, and they are based on the research question under the following statements:

- Examine the level of teachers’ motivation on students’ academic performance.
- Assess the impacts of motivation on students’ academic performance.
- Identify factors influencing teachers’ motivation towards effective performance
- Recommendations on how to motivate teachers

All the 50 questionnaires were responded to adequately; therefore, they were all analyzed. The data were analyzed using frequencies in the descriptive method and the data presented in tables.

➤ *Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents*

This section features the respondent’s demographic characteristics that were considered significant to the study. Such demographic features include sex, age, and level of

education, marital status and the duration of service. The demographic characteristics of respondents were considered significant to the study on the basis that variations on such orientations would depict different attitudes towards commitment to job performance, hence exposing human drives which may compel them in executing their duties.

- *Gender of Respondents*

This feature was considered crucial to the study for the researcher intended to establish whether gender differences would significantly influence teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Portee Community, in Eastern Freetown, owing to social gender roles that could be at variance with the prevailing working environments. In the light of this eventuality, the respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire indicating their sex and Table 3 displays their responses.

Table 3 Presentation According to Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentages %
Male	35	70
Female	15	30
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 3 depicts that of the 50 copies of questionnaire completed by the respondents, 35 (70%) were males and 15 (30%) were females. Reflected in table 3 is that, teaching at a secondary school level, seems a preserve for males. Whereas the study did not treat gender as an extraneous variable to be controlled for, the likelihood that different sexes may prefer different treatment in their duties could be a pointer to variations in commitment to job performance, though the direction of the influence envisaged was clear. However, females being responsible for a lot of other family chores were likely to be less committed in their formal duties in contrast to the male counterparts.

- *Age of the Respondents*

The researcher assumed that the age diversity of the respondents would be of great significance to the study on grounds that unemployment was rampant in the country; hence younger people were relatively few in the public sector. Moreover, age variations of the respondents could also correspond to their commitment to job performance, as young teachers may take much time to settle in respective engagements and are likely to be less committed to job performance than elderly teachers. The respondents were subsequently requested to complete the questionnaire indicating their ages and their responses recorded in Table 4.

Table 4 Presentation According to Age of the Respondents

Age in years	Frequency	Percentages %
Below 25	03	06
25- 34	12	24
35- 44	30	60
Above 45	05	10
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Indicated in Table 4.2, 03 (0.6%) of respondents whose questionnaire copies were received fell below 25 years, 12 (24%) in the age of 25-34years, 30 (60%) were in the age of 35-44, with 05 (10%) being above 45 years.

The statistics in Table 4 imply than more relatively elderly teachers than younger ones formed the bulk of the teaching fraternity in public secondary schools in Portee Community in Eastern Freetown, a sign that most of these were already carrying heavy burden of providing for their families, hence may be less committed to school duties for additional income. However, public secondary schools seem to have old employees with an optimum age bracket being 35-44 years. This is the age period within which individuals become stable in their jobs and are less inclined to seek for employment elsewhere and likely to be committed to their job performance in the hope for promotion.

- *Level of Education of the Respondents*

In the study, the researcher believed that level of education would significantly influence individual teacher's commitment to job performance, having been conditioned by strong professional ethics and codes of conducts governing any professional engagement. In this respect, the respondents were asked to fill the questionnaire stating their level of education and Table 5 displays their responses.

Table 5 Presentation according to Level of Education of the Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentages %
Certificate	10	20
Diploma	04	08
Degree	30	60
Masters	06	12
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 5 reveals that 30 (60%) of the respondents had acquired education at a degree level, 04 (08%) had diploma, 10 (20%) obtained certificate and 06 (12%) had other forms of education.

The impression created by these statistics is that secondary school level teaching is a confine of teachers with degree level, yet job performance was insufficient and hence ought to be properly motivated for increased commitment to improve job performance.

- *Marital Status of the Respondents*

This characteristic was of great importance to the study as it would help to reveal the extent to which marital status of the respondents would influence commitment to job performance on the premise that, single and married teachers being taken care of by other responsible male care takers, were likely to be less committed to their job performance than widowed female teachers whose efforts would count greatly in obtaining means of survival. In the light of this probability, the respondents were then asked to complete the questionnaire indicating their marital status and their responses were captured as illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6 Marital status of the Respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percentages %
Single	08	16
Married	26	52
Widow	07	14
Divorce	04	08
Widower	05	25
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

In Table 6, of the 50 copies of questionnaire duly completed by the respondents, 08 (16%) were single, 26 (52%) were married, 07(14%) were widowed and 04 (08%) being separated, with 05 (21.67%) having fallen on other marital orientations. The statistics in the table reveal that majority of the teachers were married and hence would have been expected to get much committed to their job performance as a way of fending for their dependents.

- *Characteristics of Respondents by Duration of Service*

In this study, it was assumed that the duration of time served in a particular learning institution would influence commitment to job performance. In this respect, young teachers on probation tend to commit their time on assigned duties to be confirmed. Similarly, teachers at the verge of promotion also work hard to achieve the desired promotion. However, teachers whose terms of service have advanced to retirement may put little efforts in their duties. On account of this eventuality, the respondents were requested to complete questionnaire stating their duration of service and their responses were noted as illustrated in Table 7.

Table 7 Characteristics of Respondents by Duration of Service

Length in Service	Frequency	Percentages %
Below 1 year	03	06
1-3	05	10
4- 6	07	14
7-9	10	20
Above 9 years	25	50
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 7 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 03 (06%) stated having served for below 1 year, 05 (10%) had served for 1-3 years, 07 (14%) indicated 4-6 years, with 10 (20%) stated 7-9 years and 25 (28.34%) having served for a duration above 9 years. Implied by the statistics in Table 4.5 is that most teachers had served for relatively long period of time, hence may have become complacent in their job performance.

➤ *Examine the Level of Teachers’ Motivation on Students’ Academic Performance.*

The information to meet this research question was sought from the respondents through questionnaires. These are the findings obtained from the study. Statements ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree of the individuals interviewed. Frequencies and percentages the teacher’s responses on the level of teacher’s motivation on students’ academic performance in the schools under review are presented below:

Table 8 Presentation according to Level of Teachers’ Motivation on Students’ Academic Performance

Statement	SA	A	NS	DA	SDA
When motivated, I attend lessons on time.	66%	20%	06%	04%	04%
Incentives from the administration boost my morale to teach	30%	30%	10%	20%	10%
Availability of teaching resources like books keeps me motivated	20%	14%	10%	50%	06%
Reinforcements determine a teacher and student’s relationship	40%	30%	10%	10%	10%
Positive reinforcement to my students makes them complete their assignment in time	50%	30%	04%	10%	06%
I arrive in school early	60%	20%	02%	12%	06%

SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, NS = Not Sure, DA = Disagree, SDA= Strongly Disagree Source: Field Data 2021

Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 33 (66%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ having motivated to attend class on time, 10 (20%) stated ‘Agreed’ when motivated to attend class on time, 03 (06%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ to attend classes on time even when motivated, with 02 (04%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 02 (04%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ having motivated to attend classes on time.

Also, Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 10 (20%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ Availability of teaching resources like books keeps me motivated, 07 (14%) stated ‘Agree’ Availability of teaching resources like books keeps me motivated, 05 (10%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ Availability of teaching resources like books keeps me motivated, with 25 (50%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 03 (06%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ Availability of teaching resources like books keeps me motivated.

Again, Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 15 (30%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ Incentives from the administration boost my morale to teach, 15 (30%) stated ‘Agreed’ Incentives from the administration boost my morale to teach, 05 (10%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ Incentives from the administration boost my morale to teach, with 10 (20%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 05 (10%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ Incentives from the administration boost my morale to teach.

Moreover, Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 25 (50%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ Positive reinforcement to my students makes them complete their assignments in time, 15 (30%) stated ‘Agree’ Positive reinforcement to my students makes them complete their assignments in time, 02 (04%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ Positive reinforcement to my students makes them complete their assignments in time, with 05 (10%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 03 (06%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ Positive reinforcement to my students makes them complete their assignments in time.

Furthermore, Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 25 (50%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ Reinforcement determine a teacher student’s relationship, 15 (30%) stated ‘Agree’ Reinforcement determine a teacher student’s relationship, 02 (04%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ Reinforcement determine a teacher student’s relationship, with 05 (10%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 03 (06%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ Reinforcement determine a teacher student’s relationship.

Finally, Table 8 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 30 (60%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ having motivated they arrive in school early, 10 (20%) stated ‘Agree’ when motivated they arrive in school early, 01 (02%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ to arrive in school early even when motivated, with 06 (12%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 02 (04%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ having motivated to arrive in school early.

Table 9 Statement how do Students Perform in CAT’s?

How do students perform in CAT’s	Frequency	Percentages %
Poorly	00	00
Well	20	40
Extremely well	30	60
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 9 reveals that 30 (60%) of the respondents stated that student perform ‘Extremely well’ in Continuous Assessment Tests (CATs), 20 (40%) stated that students perform ‘Well’ and 00 (00%) which indicate ‘Poorly’ was not selected by the respondents.

Table 10 Statement on how frequently do you Administer CAT’s

How frequently do you administer CAT’s	Frequency	Percentages %
Never	02	04
Once a term	20	40
Twice a term	23	46
Thrice a term	05	10
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

In Table 10 of the 50 copies of questionnaire duly completed by the respondents, 23 (46%) stated that, they administer cats twice, 20 (40%) indicate they administer cats once, 05 (10%) stated that, they administer cats thrice and 02 (04%) indicate they have ‘Never’ administer cats.

Table 11 Statement how do students Perform in CATs?

How do students perform in CAT’s	Frequency	Percentages %
Poorly	00	00
Well	20	40
Extremely well	30	60
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 11 reveals that 30 (60%) of the respondents stated that student perform ‘Extremely well’ in Continuous Assessment Tests (CATs), 20 (40%) stated that students perform ‘Well’ in continuous assessment tests, and 00 (00%) which indicate ‘Poorly’ was not selected by the respondents.

Table 12 Statement on whether students complete their assignment in time?

Students Complete their Assignment in Time	Frequency	Percentages %
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 12 depicts that of the 50 copies of questionnaire completed by the respondents, 40 (80%) stated ‘YES’ that students complete their assignment in time and 10 (20%) indicate that ‘NO’ students do not complete their assignments in time.

Table 13 Statement on whether students results in CAT’s reflected in the main exams?

Students Results in CAT’s Reflected in the Main Exams?	Frequency	Percentages %
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 13 depicts that of the 50 copies of questionnaire completed by the respondents, 40 (80%) stated ‘YES’ the students results in CAT’s reflected in the main exams and 10 (20%) indicate that ‘NO’ the students results in CAT’s do not reflect in the main exams.

Table 14 Statement on how do students perform in cats?

How do students perform in CAT’s	Frequency	Percentages %
Poorly	00	00
Well	20	40
Extremely well	30	60
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 14 reveals that 30 (60%) of the respondents stated that student perform ‘Extremely well’ in Continuous Assessment Tests (CATs), 20 (40%) stated that students perform ‘Well’ in continuous assessment tests, and 00 (00%) which indicate ‘Poorly’ was not selected by the respondents.

➤ *Assess the Impacts of Motivation on Students’ Academic Performance.*

Assess the impact of motivation on students’ academic performance is one of the objectives of the study. The results are presented in the Table 15 and Table 15 below respectively.

Table 15 Percentages of the Teacher’s Responses on the Impact of Motivation on Students’ Academic Performance

Statement	SA	A	NS	DA	SDA
More in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me.	62%	24%	02%	08%	04%
The in-service training influences the academic performance of my students	60%	20%	02%	12%	06%
The knowledge I acquired during my preservice training was and is still important	44%	36%	04%	08%	08%
When demotivated, I don’t deliver well	50%	20%	08%	16%	06%
My workload is manageable	42%	30%	08%	10%	10%

SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, NS = Not Sure, DA = Disagree, SDA= Strongly Disagree Source: Field data 2021

Table 15 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 30 (60%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ that the in-service training influences the academic performance of my students, 10 (20%) stated ‘Agree’ the in-service training influences the academic performance of my students, 01 (02%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ that the in-service training influences the academic performance of my students, with 06 (12%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 02 (04%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ the in-service training influences the academic performance of my students. Similarly, Table 15 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 31 (62%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ that more in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me, 12 (24%) stated ‘Agree’ more in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me, 01 (02%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ that more in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me, with 04 (08%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 02 (04%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ more in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me.

Again, Table 15 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 22 (44%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ that the knowledge I acquired during my preservice training was and is still important, 18 (36%)

stated ‘Agree’ the knowledge I acquired during my preservice training was and is still important, 02 (04%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ that the knowledge I acquired during my preservice training was and is still important, with 04 (08%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 04 (08%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ the knowledge I acquired during my preservice training was and is still important.

Furthermore, Table 15 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 25 (50%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, 10 (20%) stated ‘Agree’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, 04 (08%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, with 08 (16%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 03 (06%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ when demotivated, I don’t deliver well.

Finally, Table 15 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 21 (42%) stated ‘Strongly Agreed’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, 15 (30%) stated ‘Agree’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, 04 (08%) indicated ‘Not Sure’ that when demotivated, I don’t deliver well, with 05 (10%) stated ‘Disagree’ and 05 (10%) ‘Strongly Disagree’ when demotivated, I don’t deliver well.

Table 16 Statement on how Frequently would you Want to Take Part in the in-Service Training?

How frequently would you want to take part in the in-service training?	Frequency	Percentages %
Twice a term	17	34
Terminally	20	40
Annually	13	26
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 16 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, 20 (40%) stated that they want to participate in in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) terminally, 17 (34%) stated that they want to participate in in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) twice a term, 13 (26%) indicated that they want to participate in in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) annually.

➤ *Identify Factors Influencing Teachers’ Motivation towards Effective Performance.*

The administration is a significant part of the learning process; it’s the one that foresees the learning process, maintains a conducive environment for learning, and many more roles through various strategies. This study, however, focuses on three areas:

working conditions, promotion and remuneration.

Table 17 Identify Factors Influencing Teachers’ Motivation towards Effective Performance.

Indicators	Highly Motivates	Motivates	Highly Demotivates	Demotivates
Promotion/Recognition (praise from administration and parents)	40%	30%	10%	20%
Salary	80%	20%	00%	00%
Proper sanitation in the teaching environment	36%	28%	14%	22%
Students’ performance	36%	28%	14%	22%
Proper Staffroom facilities	42%	32%	10%	16%
Availability of teaching materials	34%	30%	16%	20%

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 17 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, According to table 10 it is revealed 18 (36%) agreed that proper sanitation in the teaching environment ‘Highly Motivates’ them, 14 (28%) indicate that proper sanitation in the teaching environment ‘Motivate’ them, 07 (14%) stated that proper sanitation in the teaching environment ‘Highly Demotivates’ them, and 11 (22%) indicate that proper sanitation in the teaching environment ‘Demotivate’ them.

Table 17 also reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, According to table 10 it is revealed 21 (42%) agreed that, proper Staffroom facilities ‘Highly Motivates’ them, 16 (32%) indicated that, proper Staffroom facilities ‘Motivate’ them, 05 (10%) stated that, Proper Staffroom facilities ‘Highly Demotivates’ them, and 08 (16%) indicated that, Proper Staffroom facilities ‘Demotivate’ them.

The table further revealed 17 (34%) agreed that Availability of teaching materials ‘Highly Motivates’ them, 15 (30%) indicate that Availability of teaching materials

‘Motivate’ them, 8 (16%) stated that Availability of teaching materials ‘Highly Demotivates’ them, and 10 (20%) indicate that Availability of teaching materials ‘Demotivate’ them.

On promotion, it involves recognition and being given more responsibility, title, and allowance. According to Table 17, 20 (40%) agreed that Promotion or recognition (praise from administration and parents) ‘Highly Motivates’ them, 15 (30%) indicated that Promotion or recognition (praise from administration and parents) ‘Motivate’ them, 5 (10%) stated that promotion/recognition (praise from administration and parents) ‘Highly Demotivates’ them, and 10 (20%) indicate that promotion/recognition (praise from administration and parents) ‘Demotivate’ them.

Finally, Table 17 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, According to table 10 it is revealed 40 (80%) agreed that salary ‘Highly Motivates’ them, 10 (20%) indicate that salary ‘Motivate’ them, while other indicators in the form of ‘Highly Demotivates’ and ‘Demotivate’ indicate 00 (00%).

Table 18 Indicators on whether Students complete their Assignment because of Proper Sanitation in the Teaching Environment

Do the students complete their assignment because of proper sanitation in the teaching environment	Frequency	Percentages %
Yes	32	64
No	18	36
Total	50	100

Source: Field Data 2021

Table 18 reveals that, of the 50 respondents whose questionnaire copies were received, the findings on table 9 shows that 32 (64%) agreed that ‘YES’ the students do complete their assignment because of proper sanitation in the teaching environment and 18 (46%) indicate that ‘NO’ the students do complete their assignment because of proper sanitation in the teaching environment.

➤ *Recommendations on how teachers should be motivated*
A - Recommendation to Administration

The administrators should provide a conducive and peaceful environment to work on, then recognize the teachers’ efforts, pay form masters allowances, appraise teachers for good performances and also help in disciplining students as well as providing teaching materials in time.

- *Recommendations to Employers*
 In this study the most advocated recommendations are;
 - ✓ *Promote the teachers and reflection of promotion allowances to avoid stagnation.*
 - ✓ *Attend to teachers' issues on time.*
 - ✓ *Offer better salary to teachers.*
 - ✓ *Provide mortgage housing facilities for teacher's retirement.*

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Introduction

This chapter gives a summary of the findings as per the data collected and analyzed in chapter four. It provides a summary, conclusion and recommendations on the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance.

B. Summary

The discussion of the data of this study focused on the finding related to the objectives of the study, which main motive seek to examine the level of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance.

➤ *Examine The Level Of Teacher's Motivation On Students' Academic Performance*

According to Javaid (2009) the level of teacher motivation and morale of teachers is determined by their conditions of living, conditions of working which then affects their performance in classroom. This implies that the level of teacher motivation is affected by various factors and it in turn affects their performance, attendance and even relation with students.

• *Class Attendance*

Respondents (teachers) were asked to provide information related to the level of teachers motivation on student academic performance. According to the result of the findings, it is worth nothing that from the respondents of the two selected secondary schools in the Portee Community in Eastern Freetown, it is reveal in table 4.6 on class attendance 33 (66%) 'Strongly Agree' that they would attend class on time when motivated. Another findings reveals in table 4.7 on students' performance in continuous assessment tests (CATs) majority of the respondents 30 (60%) stated that, students perform 'Extremely well' in continuous assessment tests. Further findings revealed that motivation from the administration of the school seem to motivate teachers as well to attend classes on time. From the findings again, it is showed that the availability of teaching and learning materials help to motivate majority of the teachers.

From the analysis above, the researcher finds out that because of the lateness or earliness of a teacher is not the only factor that affects the students' performance. This implies that the level of teacher motivation is affected by various factors and it in turn affects their performance, attendance and even relation with students. This study is perfectly in line with the empirical study below.

Atkison (2000) found out that demotivated teachers lacked the morale and enthusiasm to work or teach. This is categorized as intrinsic motivation, and it has a way of affecting the reporting time and the time taken to teach.

In Sierra Leone, secondary school lessons are allocated forty minutes and teachers are supposed to deliver exhaustively on a topic. Therefore, teachers have to be in class on time to ensure that the teaching time is maximally

used.

For effective learning, a teacher is supposed to employ various teaching methods, strategies and style. Therefore, teachers have to prepare adequately for the lessons. At the end of the day the teachers shall have played various roles in class i.e. as a planner, motivator, decision-maker and also a craftsman. As Richardson (2014) states, motivation is the interaction of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation to perform certain work to achieve goals just like the conscious and unconscious factors work hand in hand. This statement, therefore, implies that the level of teacher motivation will work hand in hand with how they appear in class, teaching method and interaction with students.

Atkison (2000) found out that demotivated teachers lacked enthusiasm in both teaching and in students work while motivated teachers had the enthusiasm and even looked forward to attend lessons and to meet their students. For instance, marking the students' work and giving extra tutorials and extra work is only possible when the teacher is well motivated.

Orji (2014) further adds that how well a teacher performs is reflected by the students' performance. Motivated teachers always teach their students well delivering all their expertise to the students but then when they lack intrinsic motivators like loving their work and extrinsic motivators like salary then their morale reduces and this can lead to reduced focus on teaching which is reflected by how late they attend lesson, how they deliver and also how early they leave the classes.

A research carried out by International institute for educational planning found out that absenteeism can be as high as 25% in other countries and this always has a negative impact on the students who are not taught and at the end of the day do not achieve the objectives of the syllabus.

• *Interaction with Students*

From the above findings and analysis, we realize that most teachers administer continuous assessment tests (CAT's) twice from the respondent 23 (46%) a term. and 20 (40%) three times a term. After a series of careful and thorough investigation of the data obtained from the respondents, it was found that, it's clear that the frequency of administering exams has a relationship with how (students) they perform. Further findings shows that continuous assessment replicate in the main the examination.

After recording the responses and discussions with the respondents of the selected secondary schools; Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School and Umar bin Al-Khattab Islamic Secondary School in the Portee Community in Eastern Freetown, the researcher found out that Positive reinforcement does not have a direct relationship with the completion of the assignment. This gives the researcher insight that other factors prompt the students to finish their work on time and not just the reinforcements from their

teachers. For example, we can say that a student's motivation is the one that determines how they complete their exams.

According to Ayo and Oji (2016), "reinforcement always strengthens the behaviour to which they are directed and that a student is always influenced by the response and reaction of the teacher to her or his behaviour." This research is in agreement with the findings of this study on teacher's reinforcement to strengthen and direct the behaviour of students.

In every learning institution there are always teachers, students, learners and support staffs, but for syllabus and education objectives to be fulfilled, it is teachers and students who must work hand in hand. Therefore, there must be positive teacher- student interaction for effective learning. In dealing with interaction of teachers with students, we looked at the how a teacher appreciated the students' attempts, to what extent a teacher went to improve the students' performance and how the teacher motivated her learners.

According to Ken Ayo Azubuike and Orji Friday Oko (2016) in their research on impacts of teachers' motivation on the academic performance of students: implication for school administration notes that the behavior of a child is always influenced by how the response and reaction of the teacher is on his or her behavior and actions. According to Boss and Vaughn (2002) it is important for teachers to recognize positive and desirable actions of students and let know they have to observe such at all times rather than only pointing their weaknesses and be verbal on them a situation that is usually there with the teachers. It should always occur to teachers that students are different and they are differently motivated, therefore, they should use different methods but then this kind of knowledge requires a teacher to be well - motivated so as to exercise patience with slow learners or geniuses in class without demotivating or insulting them. It is important for students to know teachers have high expectation for them, hence they cannot allow them to quit (Carter, 2000). Lavoit (2007) reiterates that without motivation there is no learning.

Ayo and Oji (2016) "reinforcement always strengthen the behavior to which they are directed". When a negative reinforcement is given to a student who gives an attempt in class then there is a high chance that the student will not try again in future. It is with this reason that teachers' emotions should be intact with no anger, despise or negative attitude towards a student. Birch and Ladd (1997) positive teacher-student relationship had an essential role of developing competence in a school, solved problems, and boosted the self-esteem and attention of students, which makes students perform better, and the result motivates teachers.

Davis and Ashley (2003) study preferred that teachers should put more effort in developing a good relationship with the student, which will make teachers creative in their delivery and, in turn, make the students feel safe and motivated to take intellectual risks. Successful teacher relationship makes students feel capable, and only this can

be achieved when teachers are motivated since "no blind man can lead another blind man."

- *Reporting Time in School*

After a thorough and careful investigation according to the findings of the study, it clearly shows that majority of the teachers in Sierra Leone Muslim Union Secondary School and Umar bin Al- Khattab Islamic Secondary School arrive early in school although motivation in these those schools looks low. Further findings clearly stated that some teachers are late to report to school on time because of lack of motivation.

Reporting time in school is one of the factors that help determine the level of teacher's motivation. Therefore, it's high time we find out if it affects a student's academic. From the results of the study is observed that according to respondents even though some teachers late for class pupils still perform well in continuous assessment tests. Therefore, this empirical research of Becket is in line with the findings of this study on teacher's reporting time in school early.

In Kenya, all teachers are expected to be in school from eight in the morning to five except during Fridays and Mondays when they have to be present for parade meetings with the students.

Reporting time of teachers is one of the factors that will help determine the level of teacher motivation since lateness without reasonable excuse is, of course, a sign that a teacher is not motivated and of the cause, as Leeds Becket (2018) puts it, low motivation of teachers will have a detrimental effect on the performance of the students.

- *Assess the Impacts of Motivation on Students' Academic Performance A - in-Service Training (Seminars, Conferences, and Workshops)*

Respondents (teachers) were asked to provide information related to the impacts of motivation on student academic performance. Uche (1981) stated that teachers who went for in-service training performed better as compared to the ones who attended the in-service training. According to the data collected, we can say that most teachers strongly agree and agree with Uche at a rate of 80% against 20% who are not of this idea.

Study also shows that, for the training to be more effective, majority of the teachers prefer it to be once a term to avoid distracting the teacher-student learning time. Some teachers also suggest that they prefer in-service training to be done annually for it to be effective.

Further findings of the study revealed that, there is a relationship between more in-service training to motivate teachers and how students perform in continuous assessment tests (CAT's). This is because the performance of students is not only based on the teacher preservice training. The analysis indicates that the academic performance of students is influenced by the in-service training that the teachers attend. De Jesus and Lens (2005) found out that in-service motivation played a big role in motivating teachers which in

turn influence the academic performance of the students.

Adeyemo Adeyinka and Omisore Adedotun (2013) suggested that conferences, workshops and seminars boost the growth and morale of teachers to teach students. In Greece, other than inductive training, the in-service training is optional and its aim is to support the implementation of innovative subject for high schools and it is provided by The National Organization for Teachers Training from June 2011.

In Kenya, in-service training is referred to as Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and is done to strengthen teachers professional understanding, role, context, self and sharing knowledge and activities across schools. (Githara, P.M. 2010).

Ministry of Education is the body that provides CPD courses to secondary schools in Kenya through the Kenya Education Sector Programme (KESSP). These programs are offered mostly during the April, August, and December holidays. In-service trainings are important because they foster continuous professional growth by keeping the teachers abreast of new development in their area of specialization and promote competence. Eduwen Osamwonyi (2016) states that in-service training is necessary because it enhances work performance and motivates the teacher in the field of education. It's therefore a necessity and a factor that motivates the teacher other than just keeping the teachers updated with the current innovations. When teachers attend the conferences, seminars, and workshop, they acquire knowledge which boosts their confidence and develop their intrinsic motivation. When they are back from the training, they employ the new skills that automatically reflect on students' academic performance. By 1981 in-service training was already an active process for all teachers. Uche (1981) and cross River State Government Reports (1979) confirmed that teachers who went for in-service training performed better than those who did not go for in-service training.

- *Pre-Service Training*

Preservice training on the other hand, this is the training offered before being considered legible to teach. According to Ochanji, Twoli, Bwire, and Maundu (2015) suggest that pre-service training equip teachers with skills as well as giving them confidence and morale in their work.

From the analysis of the results, we conclude that most teachers agree that pre-service training is crucial in the profession at a rate of 80%. This study is in line with what Moses et al reported. Pre-service training is a long process. For instance, in Kenya, secondary school teachers have to undergo pre-service training of three years for those who are graduating with a diploma and four years for those graduating with a degree. These teachers have a term or a year of teaching practice and as from 17 October 2019, the TSC decided and even announced internship vacancies for ten thousand teachers before they are fully employed. Other than just trying to accommodate the high demand of teachers due to 100% transition, it is a way of motivating

these trainee teachers who could be jobless for a long time and feel frustrated with education. Moses Ochanji, Nicholas Twoli, Bwire and John Maundu (2015) in their study on Mentoring in Pre- service Teacher Education: The Case of a Developing Country, Kenya suggest that pre-service training mentors and also promotes development by equipping teachers with skills that give them confidence in their work. The study further revealed that, from the respondents they indicated that their work load is manageable. This implies that the schools under survey are under staff. From the study it was revealed that, based on the data collected from the respondents they cannot deliver well when demotivated. This study is in line with what Atkison reported. Atkison (2000) found out that demotivated teachers lacked the morale and enthusiasm to work or teach. This is categorized as intrinsic motivation, and it has a way of affecting the reporting time and the time taken to teach.

- *Identify Factors Influencing Teachers' Motivation Towards Effective Performance*

Organizational strategies used to motivate teachers are also part of the motivating factors for the teachers. The study looked at other motivating factors controlled by the administration that motivate teachers' morale and also affect performance. The study was interested in working conditions, teacher remuneration, and promotion of teachers.

- *Working Conditions*

Respondents (teachers) were asked to provide information related to factors influencing teachers' motivation towards effective performance. According to findings from the analysis, we find out that there is no relationship between proper staffroom facilities and students' completion of assignments. Findings shows that, there is a relationship between proper sanitation in the teaching environment and students' completion of assignments. This study is in line with the research report of Enoch et al. Enoch Rabotapi (2016) suggested that teachers should be motivated in particular, new teachers are supposed to be taken through an induction to ease their transition into the work environment. This is probably because adapting to a new environment is not easy, and it can affect their interaction with the students hence affect students' performance. Diana Wanja Gitonga (2012), in her research on the influence of teacher motivation on students' performance in KCSE, suggests that the working condition of a teacher involves classroom conditions, workload, distance from home to work, means of communication in school, and available facilities in the school. All these have to be favourable for a teacher to be motivated enough to do his/her work. Chrispen Chiome (2016) advocates that teachers should be motivated by administrators by ensuring teachers are well informed and equipped to work in the 21st century. They need to be up to date with technology. This will also help the teacher give advanced examples in class and in turn improve students' performance. According to Anjali Sharma (2016) the working conditions of teachers have a positive correlation with the motivation of the teacher. Every administration should, therefore ensure there are

necessary facilities that motivate teachers and keep them on toes. For instance, lack of facilities like printers or fullscaps, charts, chalks, staffroom equipped with chairs can demotivate teachers and also limit the way they teach, i.e., teaching method and morale of the students hence poor performance can be noted. According to Clement Croome (2000), environment affects job performance and job satisfaction Dilani adds that there is a link between the health of an individual and the work environment by considering the sanitation, lighting, and air freshness in the rooms. Teachers' wellbeing must be prioritized by ensuring this and their morale to be boosted by keeping their environment and the classes favorable.

- *Promotion*

Promotion involves recognition and being given more responsibility, title, and allowance. According to the results of the findings, it clearly shows that majority of the respondents (teachers) stated that promotion/recognition from teachers and administration highly motivates them at a percentage of 70%. Therefore, this study is in accordance with the research reported by Dr. Walter Okibo et al. According to TSC act section 35, it is the TSC that is in charge of promoting teachers in Kenya every year. Asiago Lenah, Dr. Walter Okibo, Dr. Andrew Nyangau, and Cleophas Ondima (2015), in their research on the effects of non-financial incentives on job satisfaction of teachers in public secondary schools, found out that most teachers were demotivated by the fact that promotions from the TSC took long yet promotions was one of the main factors which boosted their morale and gave them more reasons to stay on their jobs longer that is until retirement.

- *Remuneration*

From the analysis of the study, the researcher found out that there is no direct relationship between the teachers' remuneration and students' academic performance. The performance of the students is not solely dependent on the salary of the teacher. This study is in relation to the research reported by Archingbong. Archingbong (2013) for education to be a success, there must be a continuous effort from stakeholders to provide the right working conditions, incentives, and remuneration. These are what make the teacher go to school, prepare for lessons, arrive early, and motivate learners. Prem Gaire (2015) states that when administrators provide timely pay and increase their income yearly, then teachers would be motivated to improve their performance. In Kenya, there have been several teachers' strikes based on the low salary in Kenya, and during the strikes, the students are not usually taught.

- *Recommendations on how Teachers Should be Motivated- A Recommendation to Administration*

The administrators should provide a conducive and peaceful environment to work on, then recognize the teachers' efforts, pay form masters allowances, appraise teachers for good performances and also help in disciplining students as well as providing teaching materials in time.

- *Recommendations to Employers*

In this study the most advocated recommendations are;

- ✓ Promote the teachers and reflection of promotion allowances to avoid stagnation.
- ✓ Attend to teachers' issues on time.
- ✓ Offer better salary to teachers.
- ✓ Provide mortgage housing facilities for teacher's retirement.

- C. *Conclusion*

In conclusion, the primary aim of this study was to investigate on the influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance in selected secondary schools in Portee Community in Eastern Freetown. During the investigations several ideas and issues were discovered based on the data collected from the respondents. According to the findings the researcher was able to make certain deductions which have brought a clear image of how motivation is instituted in the secondary schools. It came out clearly and was concluded that:

The researcher found out that the earliness or lateness of a teacher in class or school has no influence on the students' performance or does not affect the students' completion of assignments. This is because students' academic performance is based on many things and not time but rather on the content.

The findings of the study also revealed that, interaction of the teacher with the students influences students' academic performance; therefore, a teacher needs to have a good relationship with the students by first knowing them.

The findings also shows that, reporting time in schools under survey revealed that even though other teacher are late for school students still performed well in continuous assessments and external exams.

On the impact of motivating, the researcher found out that in-service training influences students' academic performance. However, they indicated that for it to be effective, it has to be administered in a way that does not affect learning that is by taking place terminally or annually. The researcher also found out that in-service training keeps the teacher abreast of new information and enriches their skills.

Pre-service training is essential to both the teacher and the students.

The researcher concluded that promotion motivates the teacher. As much as the working conditions of the teacher and teacher remuneration have no direct influence on the students' performance, the highly encourage teachers at a higher percentage of 80%.

Therefore, the study concluded that as much as some of the motivating factors have no direct influence on the students' performance, others have a direct impact on the

students' performance; hence it's essential for the teachers' motivation need be achieved fully.

D. Recommendations

From the study findings, there are a lot of challenges associated with motivation have been brought out. The researcher has therefore made the following recommendations for policy formulation to address these issues.

- It is therefore recommended that teachers like any other work should be motivated to increase their performance.
- It is also recommended that the management of public schools put in place measures geared towards enhancing performance of teachers and formulate motivational policies that enhance employee performance.
- The government can use the study, especially the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) in acquiring vital information critical for improving terms and working conditions of teachers in order to increase their level of motivation and job performance.
- The ministry of education (MBSSE) can use the findings from the research in understanding extrinsic rewards that lowers teacher's job performance and thus take appropriate strategies and measures so as to improve the efficiency of teachers.
- The Board of Management (BOM) can also use the findings from the research in providing rewards that give teachers impetus to work harder and facilitate pupils' performance, both in class and outside classroom.
- Since the study findings reveal that working conditions have great impact on teachers' motivation, the government should continue putting more efforts on improving the working conditions by building more houses with availability of such services as electricity and water for teachers, building laboratories with equipment and improving classrooms conditions and teaching facilities to facilitate easy teaching-learning processes.
- The Government should also review policies on secondary education. The policies should be well-designed and implemented to meet the demands of teachers; for example by making them participating and have a say on matters regarding themselves and provide them more opportunities for training and development teachers will likely be motivated.
- The government should make increase of the salaries which reflects the status of teachers and the socio-economic situation prevailing in our societies.
- The office of teaching service commission (TSC) should work hand in hand with the Central government to make sure that the implementation of the government's plans and strategies towards improving teachers' conditions are made possible with the proper allocations of funds.
- The government authorities through the ministry of finance should provide bikes on loan facilities for male teachers to facilitate their movement to attend school

early since they are dominated by male teachers.

- Increase the number of teachers to reduce the work load of other teachers.

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APPENDIX: A

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am Abass Alpha Bangura, a student at Njala University, pursuing a Master of Education Degree program. I am researching the Influence of teacher motivation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools at Portee Community, in Eastern Freetown. The study hopes to inform administrators and teachers, employers, and managers the factors that motivate teachers and how to keep teachers motivated to ensure better performance of students in public secondary schools. The research is also necessary for the successful completion of my degree studies.

I humbly request for your permission to collect data in your school. The information given will be treated as confidential and anonymous.

Yours hopeful,

Abass Alpha Bangura.

APPENDIX B: QUESTIONNAIRE

Research Questionnaire for Teachers

Research Project On Influence Of Teacher Motivation On Student's Academic Performance In Public Secondary Schools At Portee Community In Eastern Freetown

Purpose of this Questionnaire: Dear teachers, this questionnaire is developed to obtain information from the respondents on the level of teacher motivation, impacts of motivating factors on students' academic performance, and establish organizational strategies used to encourage teachers. It is divided into two sections, A and B-F, with section A, seeking for demographic characteristics of the respondents, while B-F solicits for data on the study's major variables. Diligently read the items and provide the responses sought as objectively as possible and note that any information given will be accorded utmost confidentiality.

Confidentiality: The information that you give in this questionnaire shall remain private, and the questionnaire shall be terminated after data analysis. DO NOT write your name or the name of the school. I therefore request you to answer all questions. Your honest participation is highly appreciated.

Use tick () or dot () within the brackets to mark your choice.

A. *Section A: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents*

➤ *State your sex/gender Male () Female ()*

➤ *Indicate your age bracket in years*

18-25 years () 26-35 years () 36-45 years () 46-55 years () Above 55 years ()

➤ *State your Level of Education*

Certificate () Diploma () Bachelor () Masters ()

➤ *Indicate your marital status*

Single () Married () Divorced () Widow () Widower ()

➤ *Duration of service (Work experience)*

Less than 1 years () 1-3 years () 4-6 years () 7-9 years () Above 9 years ()

B. *Section B: Examine the Level of Teachers' Motivation on Students' Academic Performance. Please Indicate how Much you Agree or Disagree with the Following by Marking One Specific Point.*

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not Sure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
When motivated,I attend lessons on time.					
Incentives fromthe administrationboost my morale to teach					
Availability ofteaching resources like books keeps me motivated					
Positive reinforcement to my studentsmakes them complete their assignmentin time					
Reinforcementsdetermine a teachersand student’s Relationship					
I arrive in schoolearly					

➤ How do the Students Perform in Continuous Assessment Tests (Cats)?

A} Poorly [] B} Well [] C} Extremely Well []

➤ How Frequently do you Administer Continuous Assessment Tests (Cats)?

A} Never [] B} Once A Term [] C} Twice A Term [] D} Three Times A Term []

➤ The student’s results in cats are reflected in the main exams. YES [] NO [] SECTION C: Assess the impacts of motivation on students’ academic performance.

Please indicate how much you agree or disagree with the following by marking one specific point.

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Not Sure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
More in-service training (conference, seminars, and workshops) motivates me.					
The in-service training influences the academicperformance of my students					
The knowledge I acquiredduring my preservice training was and is still important					
When demotivated, I don’tdeliver well					
My workload is manageable					

➤ How do the Students Perform in Continuous Assessment Tests (Cats)?

A} Poorly [] B} Well [] C} Extremely Well []

➤ How frequently would you want to take part in the in-service training?

Twice a term () Termly () Annually ()

Why.....

C. Section C: Identify Factors Influencing Teachers’ Motivation Towards Effective Performance In The Following Table, Indicate How You Feel About The Following Indicators.

Indicators	Highly Motivates	Motivates	Highly Demotivates	Demotivates
Promotion/Recognition (praisefrom administrationand parents)				
Salary				
Proper sanitationIn the teaching environment				
Students’performance				
Proper Staffroom facilities				
Availability ofteaching materials				

- *Do the students complete their assignment because of proper sanitation in the teaching environment YES [] NO []*
- *In your opinion, recommend how should the following motivate you in your teaching career?*

A.) Employer

..... B.) Administration

.....Thank You For Your Participation.